

EMERGING FOOD PATHOGENS: A CASE STUDY OF *E. Coli* 0104:H4

Bamaiyi, P.H.

Faculty of Agriculture, Adamawa State University, P.M.B. 25 Mubi, Nigeria

ABSTRACT

Food is essential for the survival of man and animals in the planet but this necessity sometimes becomes the means of destruction from the planet. Most infections that man get are either from food or water. In the last 20 years there have been several cases of food borne pathogens causing deleterious infections in man and animals. Some of these pathogens are just newly emerging and not much has been studied on them until recent times. The bulk of pathogens of food are of bacterial origin. In this review we looked at current trends in emerging food pathogens globally as it concerns the health of the almost 7 billion people on earth today and the billions of animals which are pivotal to the survival of man on the planet. We took special interest in the recent outbreak of *E. coli* 0104:H4 that started from Germany and spread to some other parts of Europe and the United States of America. This outbreak was attributed to infected cucumbers, bean sprouts, lettuce and tomatoes whose origin seems difficult to determine with certainty. Some suggestions are offered on the way forward when confronted with pandemic infections in an increasingly global village that the world has become.

KEY WORDS: Emerging pathogens, *E. coli* 0104:H4, food, bacteria

INTRODUCTION

Food pathogens of concern to public health include pathogenic strains of bacteria, viruses, helminthes, protozoa and algae, and certain toxic products they may produce. Foodborne infections are caused when microorganisms are ingested, and these can multiply in the human body. Intoxications result when microbial or naturally occurring toxins are consumed in contaminated foods. Microorganisms or toxins may be introduced directly from infected food animals or from workers, other foods, or the environment during the preparation or processing of food. Poisonous substances may also be produced by the growth of bacteria and molds in food (Buncic, 2006; WHO, 2011). Table 1 lists pathogenic organisms of public health importance, which may be transmitted through contaminated food.

Table 1: Examples of main biological hazards in foods

Bacteria (spore-forming)	Viruses
<i>Clostridium botulinum</i>	Hepatitis A and E
<i>Clostridium perfringens</i>	Norwalk virus group
<i>Bacillus cereus</i>	Rotavirus
Bacteria (non-spore-forming)	Protozoa and parasites
<i>Brucella abortus</i>	<i>Cryptosporidium parvum</i>
<i>Brucella suis</i>	<i>Diphyllobothrium</i>
<i>Campylobacter spp.</i>	<i>Entamoeba histolytica</i>
Pathogenic Escherichia coli (<i>E. coli</i> O157:H7, EHEC, EIEC, ETEC, EPEC)	<i>Giardia lamblia</i>
	<i>Ascaris lumbricoides</i>
	<i>Taenia solium</i>
<i>Listeria monocytogenes</i>	<i>Taenia saginata</i>
<i>Salmonella spp.</i> (<i>S. typhimurium</i> , <i>S. enteritidis</i>)	<i>Trichinella spiralis</i>
<i>Shigella (S. dysenteriae)</i>	
<i>Staphylococcus aureus</i>	
<i>Streptococcus pyogenes</i>	
<i>Vibrio cholera</i>	
<i>Vibrio parahaemolyticus</i>	
<i>Vibrio vulnificus</i>	
<i>Yersinia enterocolytica</i>	

Source: FAO (1998) *Food Quality and Safety Systems*

The most commonly recognized food borne infections are those caused by the bacteria *Campylobacter*, *Salmonella*, and *E.coli O157:H7*, and by a group of viruses called *calicivirus*, also known as the *Norwalk* and *Norwalk-like* viruses. But many other pathogens cause food borne infections in different parts of the world. Some more common in certain places than others places depending on the optimum conditions for the organism and food habits of people in various geographical locations of the world.

Foodborne diseases are one of the most widespread problems of the contemporary world, and are an important cause of economic loss (Newell *et al.*, 2010). The diseases are toxic or infectious by nature and illnesses result from ingestion of contaminated food or water. The causative agents can be chemical like pesticide residues and toxic metals or biological, like pathogenic microorganisms. Illnesses caused by plant toxicants and mycotoxins are also regarded as foodborne diseases. The clinical picture for foodborne disease may be mild when symptoms include nausea, vomiting and self-limiting diarrhoea, but can also be severe when there are serious disorders of the nervous system and diarrhoea is life-threatening. Every year the World Health Organization (WHO) receives reports of foodborne diseases from all over the world. These reports seem to indicate an increase over the past few years, with biologically contaminated foods being the major cause of illness (Newell *et al.*, 2010).

How these pathogens act and emerge

The pathogenic spectrum can change substantially over time. This happens for several reasons. Pathogens for which transmission is well understood may ultimately be controlled. Others may emerge through mutation, or may move into a new niche in the food chain. As a result, the frequency of specific infections can change substantially, reflecting a balance between the ecologies that support bacterial populations that contaminate food, and the cultural habits, and technologies that limit or prevent that contamination from occurring. For example, in the first decades of the 1900s, some of the principal infections that were recognized as foodborne included typhoid fever, tuberculosis, brucellosis, and septic sore throat, a zoonotic streptococcal infection (Tauxe, 2002). These conditions have largely disappeared from the industrialized world as foodborne diseases, as a result of milk sanitation and pasteurization, disease control efforts in animals, better regulation of shellfish beds, and other measures. Trichinosis, which was once common, also virtually disappeared by the 1970s when the practice of feeding pigs uncooked garbage was ended (Schantz, 1983). When it does occur, it is almost exclusively among ethnic groups that eat raw pork or horse meat. More recently, outbreaks of food poisoning caused by *Staphylococcus aureus* and by *Clostridium perfringens* have become uncommon in the United States, for reasons that remain to be clarified (Duffy *et al.*, 2008; Newell *et al.*, 2010).

Although many foodborne infections have been controlled, there is still the burden of foodborne disease. For example from statistics in the United States, it has been estimated that the annual burden stands at 76 million cases of illness, 323,000 hospitalizations per year, and 5000 deaths. This means that 1 in 4 Americans gets a foodborne illness each year, and more than 1 in 1000 is hospitalized. This estimate was arrived at by estimating the proportion of the population that gets a significant gastrointestinal illness each year, and then estimating the proportion of gastrointestinal illness that is likely to be foodborne. Thus, the estimate of foodborne illness is the total incidence of acute gastrointestinal illness, about 79 illness episodes per 100 persons per year, and the fraction of 36% estimated as foodborne, or 28 per 100 per year. This large burden means that there are still many foodborne infections to be controlled, despite the successes of the 20th century (Mead *et al.*, 1999).

There are 27 principal foodborne pathogens reported and 13 of them have been identified as foodborne pathogens only within the last 25 years. Some, like *Escherichia coli O157:H7*, are likely to have evolved relatively recently, and may represent genuinely new pathogens (Oliver *et al.*, 2010; Tauxe, 2002).

Some new food borne infectious tendencies

There are a number of characteristics of the modern landscape of foodborne disease. First is the global dissemination of some foodborne pathogens in pandemic form such as Salmonellosis (Mukhopadhyay and Ramaswamy, 2011). For example, in the 1980s, a few strains of *Salmonella enteritidis* swept through the egg laying and broiler flocks of much of the world, making it the most common *Salmonella* serotype worldwide. The exact means of dissemination has yet to be clarified, and it involved more than one strain, as defined by phage susceptibility or pulsed field gel electrophoresis genotyping. The peculiar property of these strains to seek the ovarian tissues of the hen, and to infect the eggs, usually without causing overt pathology in either hen or egg, suggests that this virulence capacity itself might be what was disseminated (Dourou *et al.*, 2011; Hue *et al.*, 2008). Australia and New Zealand remain unaffected by this global pandemic. Something similar has happened

with highly resistant strains of *Salmonella typhimurium*, defined by phage typing as type 104. These strains emerged in the 1990s in Europe and North America simultaneously, first in cattle and then in other animals (Tauxe, 2002). These DT104 complex strains have since appeared in many other parts of the world, though again, not in Australia or New Zealand. The fact that neither *S. enteritidis* nor *S. typhimurium* DT104 has appeared in Australia or New Zealand offers an important clue as to how such strains spread. Human carriers and wild birds which travel freely did not introduce these strains. If they spread through shipments of live animals and feedstuffs, the tight quarantine controls on such shipments in those two countries might have kept them out (Crump *et al.*, 2001). The resistance genes are encoded on chromosomal integrons, and may themselves be the mobile pandemic element. A third example of a global pandemic is the appearance of *Yersinia enterocolitica* strains of serogroups O3 and O9 in Europe, Japan in the 1970s, and in North America by the end of the 1980s. These strains appear to have a reservoir in pigs, where they cause little more than pharyngitis, but are transmitted to humans by consumption of or contact with raw pork or pork products. The mechanism of spread of these strains among pig herds is unclear, but may be related to the exchange of breeding stocks.

Increasing antimicrobial resistance is another general trend among the foodborne bacterial pathogens. For those with primary human reservoirs, such as *Shigella* spp. and *S. typhi*, the agent of typhoid fever, the emergence of resistance is related to the use of antibiotic agents in human populations. However, for those pathogens with primary food animal reservoirs, the principal driver of increasing resistance is the use of antibiotics in agriculture (Newell *et al.*, 2010; White *et al.*, 2002). This use, for purposes of disease treatment and for growth promotion, contributes to the selection of resistant strains and to their subsequent spread. For example, the use of a fluoroquinolone in a chicken flock can convert or replace the prevalent *C. jejuni* strains from 100% susceptibility to 100% resistance within days. The use of therapeutic third generation cephalosporins in cattle may be associated with the disturbing appearance of *Salmonella* strains resistant to ceftriaxone. The longstanding use of the combination dalfopristin/quinupristin in chickens meant that when these agents were later approved for use in human medicine to treat infections with vancomycin-resistant *Enterococcus*, strains of *Enterococcus* spp. That had developed resistance to these agents were already present in poultry meat. The appearance of linked resistance, such as the penta-resistance of DT104 strains of *S. typhimurium*, is of particular concern, as the use of any member of the five agent classes may select for the presence of all five resistance genes. Thus, this strain will have a selective advantage where ampicillin-like agents, florfenicol, streptomycin, sulfonamides, or tetracyclines, are used (Banerjee and Sarkar, 2004; Newell *et al.*, 2010; White *et al.*, 2002).

A new wave of outbreak and emergence of *E. coli* O104:H4

In recent years, highly dispersed outbreaks are being recognized more frequently as microbial subtyping systems such as serotyping or pulsed field gel electrophoresis are used. These dispersed outbreaks do not present as a sharp local increase in cases, but rather as a diffuse increase in the number of apparently sporadic cases in several jurisdictions. These outbreaks are caused by foods that may be contaminated at a low level before they are shipped from a central facility to many places. The increase in cases in any one place may not be sufficient to attract notice, so these outbreaks may only be detected because the bacterial strains are received and subtyped in public health laboratories, allowing strains from many jurisdictions to be compared, as happens with PulseNet in the United States and EnterNet in Europe. Investigation may identify a systematic problem in production or processing with implications for the entire industry. Identifying and investigating these industrial scale outbreaks drive the cycle of prevention faster (Newell *et al.*, 2010; Tauxe, 2002).

In recent years, such kind outbreaks have been dramatic, and investigations of them have led to crucial advances in foodborne disease prevention. In 1997, shortly after the state health department of Colorado started testing their *E. coli* O157:H7 isolates in PulseNet, 16 cases of infection with the same unusual pattern were detected in Colorado and a state closeby. These cases were linked to ground beef produced at a large factory. Because that plant had the habit of carrying over leftover beef from one production lot and working it into subsequent day's production, thereby contaminating that lot, an astounding 25 million pounds of meat was recalled, and the habit was strongly discouraged throughout the industry (Tauxe, 2002).

The organism *E. coli* was first isolated by T. Escherich in 1885 and was named after him. There are mainly 6 groups:

- i. Enterohaemorrhagic *E. coli* (EHEC)
- ii. Enterotoxigenic *E. coli* (ETEC)
- iii. Enteropathogenic *E. coli* (EPEC)
- iv. Enteroinvasive *E. coli* (EIEC)
- v. Enteroadherent *E. coli* (EAEC)
- vi. Enteroaggregative *E. coli* (EAggEC)

There are more than 700 serotypes of the organism *E. coli* and till now no vaccine has been produced against this infectious organism. These serotypes are identified based on changes in their surface “O” antigens such as *E. coli* 0157 or *E. coli* 055 as indicated by immunological tests. *E. coli* strains are further differentiated using “H” antigens. They are opportunistic pathogens that reside within the gastrointestinal tract but do not usually cause infections within the gastrointestinal tract but outside of it such as the urinary tract (Davis, 2011; Tauxe, 2002).

E. coli O157:H7 is strain of the gram negative bacterial pathogen *E. coli* that has a reservoir in cattle and other similar animals. It was first recognized as a pathogen in 1982 (Riley *et al.*, 1983). It is a shigatoxin producing *E. coli* and produces 2 different shiga toxins tagged Stx1 and Stx2. Ingestion of only 10-100 organisms is enough to produce infection. Human illness typically follows consumption of food or water that has been contaminated with microscopic amounts of cow feces. The illness it causes is often a severe and bloody diarrhea and painful abdominal cramps, without much fever. In 3% to 5% of cases, a complication called hemolytic uremic syndrome (HUS) can occur several weeks after the initial symptoms. This kind of severe complication manifests as temporary anemia, profuse bleeding, and kidney failure (Breum and Boel, 2010; Newell *et al.*, 2010; Wang *et al.*, 2011).

E. coli 0104:H4

Scientists have suggested that *E. coli* 0104:H4 is a mutant that emanated from *E. coli* 0157:H7. Food such as cucumbers, lettuce, tomatoes and bean sprouts have been mainly implicated in the latest outbreak of food borne *E. coli* 0104:H4 that was first reported in Germany and spread to some other European countries and the United States of America. Many have died from infection by these bacteria and thousands have taken ill and were hospitalized. Most of the victims contrary to some previous food borne illnesses were not children but middle aged individuals and more women than men were affected. In Germany most of the cases were clustered around Hamburg, Germany (Marler, 2011; Perrett, 2011).

Fig.1: Cucumber suspected to be infected with Shiga toxin

It is seen as an enterotoxigenic and enterohaemorrhagic *E. coli* strain. It produces a shigatoxin which is one of the most potent toxins known to man so much that the Centre for Disease Control has listed it a bioterrorism weapon (Kogan *et al.*, 1992; Martin *et al.*, 2011; Wang *et al.*, 2001). The cycle involved in transmitting the

infection is simple as man usually gets it from the contamination of food by animals (Figure 2) especially the faeces of ruminants. Animals transmit it to man and then it is followed by person to person transmission.

Fig. 2: Cycle of events involved in transmitting a Shiga toxin from a ruminant to man (Dr Rao: <http://www.slideshare.net/doctorrao/ecoli-0104-h4-an-emerging-infection>)

The genetic code for this new virulent strain of *E. coli* has been described which agrees with earlier work done on this strain years before this outbreak (Martin *et al.*, 2011; Wang *et al.*, 2001). This strain which closely resembles *E. coli* 0157:H7 produce a toxin which resembles that of *Shigella dysenteriae*. It is suggested that the picking up of new genes by horizontal transfer is what has led to the emergence of such a deadly new strain of bacteria. Once it is incorporated into the new genome, the new gene can provide the bacteria with novel properties. This must have led to the *E. coli* 0104 outbreak in recent times considered the worse in Europe in recent history. The strain is considered a hybrid strain of two different *E. coli* strains and the genetic code (figure 3) was described by German and Chinese scientist comparable to earlier works on the organism (Martin *et al.*, 2011; Wang *et al.*, 2001).

The *E. coli* infection seems to affect more women than men probably because women tend to eat more fresh vegetables than men (Perrett, 2011). The infection leads to haemolytic uremic syndrome (HUS) which is as a result of the impairment of the kidneys function by the shiga toxin produced. Early diagnosis minimizes the risk of renal damage.

Fig. 3: Gene code for new strain of *E. coli* responsible for latest *E. coli* infection (European press photo agency 2011)

Selective medium can be used for the diagnosis of the infection by taking faecal samples from suspected cases. Treatment is usually supportive and the use of antibiotics to treat is discouraged. Moreover, this new strain has been found to be resistant to most antibiotics that are usually used for treatment. Prevention of the infection is by simple rules of hygiene such as hand washing; food must be cooked before eating; avoid raw unpasteurized milk; avoid swallowing water when swimming and avoid cross contamination of food.

CONCLUSION

Food borne pathogens keep on emerging and re-emerging with changing human eating habits, increase in demand for all sorts of exotic food, increase in global market in vegetables and with increase in travel around the world now an epidemic in one country, if not properly controlled can spread to other countries within hours. The recent *E.coli* 0104:H4 outbreak is a classic example because within a few days it has spread to many nations in Europe and to the United States of America. Dynamic measures must be put in place to monitor such pathogens from farm to fork and from stable to table in order to ensure healthy food for the benefit of the human community. Early detection of food contamination at the farm level before the food goes to the market will ensure maximum protection of lives. If such detection mechanisms had been properly in place and utilized the vegetables responsible for the human lives lost due to *E.coli* 0104:H4 would have been detected and lives and resources would have been saved. It is clear that more needs to be done if humanity is to win the battle against food pathogens which in recent times are becoming more resistant to antibiotics (White *et al.*, 2002).

REFERENCES

- Banerjee, M., and Sarkar, P. K. (2004). Antibiotic resistance and susceptibility to some food preservative measures of spoilage and pathogenic micro-organisms from spices. *Food Microbiology*, 21(3), 335-342.
- Breum, S. Ø., and Boel, J. (2010). Prevalence of *Escherichia coli* O157 and verocytotoxin producing *E. coli* (VTEC) on Danish beef carcasses. *International Journal of Food Microbiology*, 141(1-2), 90-96.
- Buncic, S. (Ed.). (2006). Integrated Food Safety and Veterinary Public Health Trowbridge: Cromwell Press, Trowbridge, UK
- Crump, J. A., Murdoch, D. R., and Baker, M. G. (2001). Emerging infectious diseases in an island ecosystem: the New Zealand perspective. *Emerging Infectious Diseases* 7, 767-772.
- Davis, C. P. (2011). *E. coli* 0157:H7 (*Escherichia coli* 0157:H7 infection). Retrieved 16.06.11, 2011, from http://www.medicinenet.com/e_coli__0157h7/article.htm
- Dourou, D., Ammor, M. S., Skandamis, P. N., and Nychas, G.-J. E. (2011). Growth of *Salmonella enteritidis* and *Salmonella typhimurium* in the presence of quorum sensing signalling compounds produced by spoilage and pathogenic bacteria. *Food Microbiology*, 28(5), 1011-1018.
- Duffy, G., Lynch, O. A., and Cagney, C. (2008). Tracking emerging zoonotic pathogens from farm to fork. *Meat Science*, 78(1-2), 34-42.
- Hue, O., Le Bouquin, S., Lalande, F., Allain, V., Rouxel, S., Petetin, I., *et al.* (2008). Prevalence of *Salmonella* spp. on broiler chicken carcasses and risk factors at the slaughterhouse in France in 2008. *Food Control*, 22(8), 1158-1164.
- Kogan, G., Jann, B., and Jann, K. (1992). Structure of the *Escherichia coli* 0104 polysaccharide and its identity with the capsular K9 polysaccharide. *FEMS Microbiology Letters*, 91(2), 135-140.
- Marler, W. (2011). E.Coli 0104:H4 Outbreak. Retrieved 07.06.11, 2011, from <http://www.foodpoisonjournal.com/foodborne-illness-outbreaks/e-coli-o104h4-outbreak>
- Martin, T. W., Stevens, L., and Miller, J. W. (2011). Rare germ drives outbreak. Retrieved 16.06.11, 2011, from <http://online.wsj.com/article/SB10001424052702303745304576360780812512492.html>

Mead, P. S., Slutsker, L., Dietz, V., McCaig, L. F., Bresee, J. S., Shapiro, C., *et al.* (1999). Food-related illness and death in the United States. *Emerging Infectious Diseases* 5, 607-625.

Mukhopadhyay, S., and Ramaswamy, R. (2011). Application of emerging technologies to control Salmonella in foods: A review. Food Research International, In Press, Corrected Proof.

Newell, D. G., Koopmans, M., Verhoef, L., Duizer, E., Aidara-Kane, A., Sprong, H., *et al.* (2010). Food-borne diseases -- The challenges of 20 years ago still persist while new ones continue to emerge. *International Journal of Food Microbiology*, 139(Supplement 1), S3-S15.

Oliver, D. M., Page, T., Heathwaite, A. L., and Haygarth, P. M. (2010). Re-shaping models of *E. coli* population dynamics in livestock faeces: Increased bacterial risk to humans? *Environment International*, 36(1), 1-7.

Perrett, H. (2011). More women than men are becoming ill and dying from contaminated cucumbers. Retrieved 09.06.11, 2011, from <http://thesafefoodhandbook.blogspot.com/2011/05/more-women-than-men-are-developing-hus.html>

Riley L.W., Remis R.S., Helgerson S.D., McGee H.B., Wells J.G., Davis BR, *et al.* (1983) [Hemorrhagic colitis associated with a rare *Escherichia coli* serotype](#). *New England Journal of Medicine*, (308), 681–685.

Schantz, P. (1983). Trichinosis in the United States-1947-1981. *Food Technology* 37, 83-86.

Tauxe, R. V. (2002). Emerging foodborne pathogens. *International Journal of Food Microbiology*, 78(1-2), 31-41.

Wang, L., Briggs, C. E., Rothmund, D., Fratamico, P., Luchansky, J. B., and Reeves, P. R. (2001). Sequence of the *E. coli* O104 antigen gene cluster and identification of O104 specific genes. *Gene*, 270(1-2), 231-236.

Wang, H., Cheng, H., Wei, D., and Wang, F. (2011). Comparison of methods for measuring viable *E. coli* cells during cultivation: Great differences in the early and late exponential growth phases. *Journal of Microbiological Methods*, 84(1), 140-143.

White, D. G., Zhao, S., Simjee, S., Wagner, D. D., and McDermott, P. F. (2002). Antimicrobial resistance of foodborne pathogens. *Microbes and Infection*, 4(4), 405-412.

WHO. (2011). Food Safety. Retrieved 09.06.11, 2011, from <http://www.who.int/foodsafety/en/>.

Received for Publication: 14/05/2011

Accepted for Publication: 10/08/2011

Corresponding author

Present Address: Department of Pathology and Microbiology, Faculty of Veterinary Medicine, Universiti Putra Malaysia

Veno@phbamaiyi.com; bamaiyip@adsu.edu.ng